

Radiating Charge and Changes in Internal Versus External Variables Part II

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Newtonian mechanics describes the dynamics of large objects consisting of many molecules by considering changes of a single external-collective variable, the center-of-mass position. Newtonian objects have a temperature, but these degrees of freedom are not considered in Newtonian dynamics. In a tiny dx region (with $dx \rightarrow 0$) the center-of-mass spatial variable x has various derivative values and each of these exact values also apply to each point in the large body (assume only translation, no rotation). Thus, at each dx and t , one has a snapshot of a collective body with all chunks moving in the same way, at least in the case of rigid body (i.e. no translations only, no vibrations etc.)

Maxwell wrote electromagnetic equations based on experimental results to describe charged particles and electric and magnetic fields. Lorentz also added an expression for force. The question we ask is: Do the dynamics of a moving (possibly accelerating) charged particle coincide with Newtonian mechanics? In Part I, we suggested that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations not only deal with the center-of-mass collective-external variable, but also with internal variables. We suggested that this was due to the fact that a second time derivative of the dipole moment exists. The first d/dt derivative simply describes translational motion. Here we note that the time derivatives appear in the first place because one uses retarded time $t-R/c$.

Here we suggest that using retarded time breaks with Newtonian mechanics. As noted above, at each t , the center of mass is at $x(t)$ and has a velocity v which is the same as the translational velocity for each chunk in the large body. In other words, one has a system with v_1 at x_1 and at x_2 a system with v_2 . In the case of an accelerating charged particle, one would need to have a snapshot at x_1 with all points having v_1 and at x_2 , a snapshot of all points having v_2 . In fact, Maxwell's electromagnetic theory allows one to describe the E and B fields of a charge with a constant v . The retarded time, however, breaks this Newtonian picture and describes acceleration effects due to retarded time throughout space. These effects are not part of Newtonian mechanics which is only interested in x_1, t_1, v_1 at each dx . These changes, which are physically linked with rearrangements of the charge distribution, and hence E and B field contributions, must represent something other than the Newtonian picture of a moving object. These E and B fields, however, represent energy and momentum density. This implies that there exists such densities which are not part of the translating body. If one assumes that there is no collective energy stirred (rotation, vibration etc) and does not allow for heat in the field, then it seems that this extra energy, momentum must be shed as it is in the form of radiation.

(One may note that retarded time creates internal degrees of freedom due to changes even in a non charged particle system as we discuss in the note.)

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics for a translating rigid body (with no rotation, vibration or other collective modes) deals with a single spatial point, the center-of-mass position. If the particle is at x , it is assumed to be within dx at x with $dx \rightarrow 0$. The center-of-mass position has a velocity (dx/dt), acceleration $d/dt dx/dt$ etc. These values, it seems, are applied to each little chunk of matter in the large Newtonian object. In other words, one seems to have snapshots, with the same values v , dv/dt in each chunk, rather than a dynamic change throughout the Newtonian body.

The question which arises is: Does this picture apply to a moving/accelerating charge distribution?

Electromagnetism

Classical electromagnetism is described by Maxwell's laws, which are based on experiment, and Lorentz's force expression. These laws deal with force felt by a charged particle/distribution due to electric E and B fields and the fields created by such a distribution. It is assumed that Newtonian mechanics still holds. For example, one may write a Lagrangian for a charged particle moving in E and B fields. The first step is to write E and B in terms of a scalar electric potential ϕ and magnetic vector potential A :

$$E \text{ vector} = -\text{grad } \phi - d/dt A \text{ partial } ((1a)) \quad B \text{ vector} = \text{grad } \times A \quad ((1b))$$

Then, a charged particle moving in E and B fields is described by the Hamiltonian:

$$H = (p - e/c A) \text{ dot } (p - e/c A) + q \phi \quad ((2))$$

Here p is not the momentum of the particle, but rather:

$$P = mv + e/c A \quad ((3))$$

If Newtonian mechanics applies to a charged particle in E and B fields, what about the motion of a charge distribution moving/accelerating in no E, B fields, but creating its own E and B fields?

It is possible to calculate the E and B fields for a point charged particle moving with a constant v . The E field is no longer spherical and there is an additional B field when it moves. Furthermore, there are energy and momentum densities given by:

$$\text{Energy density} = c_1 E \text{ dot } E + c_2 B \text{ dot } B \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{Momentum density} = c_3 E \times B \quad ((4b))$$

If $E(v)$ and $B(v)$, then there is an extra energy in the fields of the moving point charged particle associated with special relativity. Thus, not only the rest mass of the core of the charge distribution changes due to v .

Given the above ideas, it seems that electromagnetism is completely consistent with Newtonian mechanics at first, but considerations of an accelerating charge distribution seem to suggest a partial break.

Accelerating Charge Distribution

If one has a small charge (or charge distribution) with most of the mass (energy) of the system and all of the charge, then there are E and B fields existing out in a large region of space around this small region. An interaction with the tiny central region leads to changes which must then be propagated out in space (to the fields) and this cannot happen at a speed faster than c, presumably, hence the retarded time given by:

$$T - R/c \text{ where } T \text{ is time and } R = |\mathbf{r} \text{ vector} - \mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}| \quad ((5))$$

\mathbf{r}' is the vector from an origin to a piece of the charge distribution, \mathbf{r} vector is the distance from the origin to a measurement point P far away and R is the vector $|\mathbf{r} \text{ vector} - \mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}|$. Thus, there will be time changes due to translation.

We suggest that using retarded time breaks with the Newtonian picture of having a snapshot of the system at t , x_1 with each point having v_1 and then moving to x_2 at t_2 with v_2 , Electromagnetism, when using retarded time, seems to show the evolution of the effects of a force on a tiny core charge distribution as they affect outer field regions in time. One no longer has a rigid body, but rather internal degrees of freedom being excited.

It is known that the electric and magnetic field distributions differ for v_1 and v_2 , even in a static picture (no acceleration). Thus, the presence of acceleration (i.e. second derivative of d/dt) in the electromagnetic equations should show the dynamics of acceleration throughout the large spatial regions with E and B fields, something that is not shown in Newtonian mechanics.

In other words, there may be components of the E and B strictly associated with the dynamics of acceleration in the retarded time situation. These are not the E and B components of a charge distribution at x_1 with v_1 or x_2 with v_2 , but they represent energy density and momentum density. The question is: Where does this energy and momentum density go? If it cannot go into some collective mode or into temperature, then it seems that it must be jettisoned, i.e. photons must be radiated. This is in complete contrast with Newtonian mechanics which ignores the details of acceleration as it occurs throughout the large Newtonian body.

Given that one has retarded time, this retardation does not only affect the E and B fields out in space, but also the charge distribution density. Thus, the actual charge distribution is changing, not just due to translation, but is reconfiguring due to time retardation. This is not a translation effect and suggests internal degrees of freedom being invoked in a non-collective manner, as suggested in Part I. These, in turn, give rise to E and B contributions which are non-collective and ultimately lead to radiated photons.

To see specifically the effects of time retardation and how it lead to special E and B non-collective components, consider (here we follow (1))

Charge density(r' vector, $t-R/c$) ((6)) (using the definitions given in ((5)))

If this is expanded in a Taylor series, then:

Charge density = density(r' vector, $t-r$ vector/ c) + $r' \cdot r / cr$ d density/dt partial (at r' vectr $t-r/c$) + ... ((7))

Given that: electric potential = $\phi = c \int \text{charge density } dv' / R$ ((8))

one may expand $1/R$, to obtain:

$$1/R = 1/r + (1/r)(1/r) r' \cdot r / r + \dots$$

One may see that ϕ becomes:

$$\Phi = c \{ q/r + r \cdot p(t-r/c)/(r^3) + r \cdot dp/dt (t-r/c)/ (cr^2) \} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, one has q , the total charge, p , the dipole distribution and dp/dt , the time change of the dipole distribution. Even a translating charge distribution has a $d/dt p$ (i.e. a time derivative of a dipole distribution). If a second time derivative d/dt , however, also exists, then one no longer has the same charge distribution because each chunk of charge is not accelerating at the same time and so does not have the same v at the same time. Thus, a Newtonian large body is synchronous, but a charge distribution is not, due to retarded time.

To consider an analogy, imagine that one has a row of runners all running at a constant v . If the first runner is told to accelerate and after 1 sec tell the second runner to accelerate, then the distance between the first and second runners changes, due to time retardation. In other words, the "charge" distribution changes. This means that there are internal degrees of freedom which change.

To explicitly see these external degrees of freedom affecting E and B fields, one may follow (1) and Part I as well. Using the expressions ((1a)) and ((1b)) for E and B (with A being defined as:

$$A = c^2 \int dv' J(r' t-r/c + r' \cdot r / cr) / \{ r - (r' \cdot r) / r \} \quad ((10))$$

One may find that taking d/dt partial or d/dr does not only act on the collective $1/r$ in the denominator, but also on the internal degrees of freedom in the dipole moment. Thus, a d/dt partial or d/dr may leave $1/r$ alone and change the derivative of p or dp/dt . As a result, as argued in Part I, there are components of B and E which drop as $1/r$, which is not the usual charged particle or charged distribution result. Thus, something else is happening due to time retardation which is akin to non-collective motion or to internal degrees of freedom obtaining their own energy and momentum density.

The last feature is that these internal degrees of electromagnetic energy and momentum density are no longer bound to the original particle (as they are not part of the usual force profile) and they move on their own, i.e. as radiated photons).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics of a large translating rigid object with no collection motion except translation, deals with a single variable, the center-of-mass position. The center-of-mass has $x, t, dx/dt$ and $d/dt dx/dt$ values and these same values pertain to each chunk of the rigid body. It is as if one has a snapshot of a particle with at each x_1, t_1, v_1 with no explicit effects of acceleration affecting the rigid body (except that at the next dx , its v has changed to $v+dv$).

We ask whether this static approach applies to an accelerating charge distribution? If one follows the Newtonian approach, then at each x (within dx), one has a particle with velocity v . In electromagnetism, one may calculate the E and B fields for a constant v . At the next dx , one has $v+dv$, and one may calculate the new E and B fields. In other words, one does not see the dynamics as the acceleration effects spread throughout space where the E and B fields exist. This is like instantaneous change, i.e. no retarded time.

Maxwell's electromagnetic equations using retarded time, however, specifically indicate that changes due to acceleration are asynchronous. This, in turn, leads to spatial changes even of the charge distribution (beyond translation) and also to corresponding E and B fields. In other words, internal degrees of freedom emerge which are not part of collective motion. These have E and B components which in turn are linked to electric/magnetic energy and momentum densities which are not part of a collective object. These seem to exist on their own and become radiated photons, we suggest.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory. Addison-Wesley 1980. Pp 458-459